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“THE SOLDIER'S LEGACY”

He stood so tall in uniform,
Our father, answering the call of duty.
The genuine and ferocious heart of a soldier,
We always knew, though, that it was soft for family.

He rose with the weight of combat every morning.
Despite his predicament, he provided affection.
During the interminable days and restless nights,
He protected us from all of our troubles.

His strength was unknown, and his hands were weathered.
Through heat and cold, through rain and shine.
He took the burden for Mom and us.
by silent suffering and sacrifice.

Wearing well-worn boots, he would march off.
Thoughts of being confined at home would brighten his day.
For Mother dear and three tiny hearts,
He battled to drive out fear and doubt.

A table was minimal, yet love was profound.
He would always retain his dreams for us.
Although a soldier's pay is seldom very high,
still created a lasting future.

His tales illuminated our eyes at night.
Of bravery discovered beneath a stern sky.
However, he never voiced any complaints.
He covered up his pain and his wounds.

He fought for us, giving it his best.
Despite difficulties, he would never falter.
Strong, unwavering, and honest, our hero

His greatest triumph was the expansion of our family.

Even though time may rob and battle may fade,
We will never forget the strength he showed.

Because we learned to soar in his love,
The heart of a soldier never stops beating.

